

Relationship between Teacher Identified Regulation, Teacher Introjected regulation, Teacher External Regulation and Student Academic performance in Kenya: A study across Secondary Schools in Gem Sub County

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ABSTRACT: Studies on teacher motivation in Pakistan and Zambia indicate low teacher motivation resulting to low student academic performance. In Kenya, low teacher motivation was found in Masaba South Sub-County, Ugenya Sub-County and Gem Sub-County which also resulted to low student academic performance. A preliminary survey conducted in five poorly performed schools in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education examination in Gem Sub-County revealed that between 2011-2013 absenteeism was reported in 4 (80%) schools, lack of co-operation from teachers 3(60%) schools, lateness 4 (80%) schools, missing classes 5 (100%) schools and resignation from teaching 1(20%) school. Gem Sub-County also experienced low student academic performance between 2011 - 2013 with a mean of 5.231, lower than Ugenya, Siaya, and Ugunja Sub-Counties with a mean of 6.023, 5.904 and 5.350 respectively for the same period in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education examination. The Objectives of the study were to establish the relationship between teacher identified regulation, teacher introjected regulation, teacher external regulation and student academic performance. The study revealed that Teacher identified regulation had a weak, positive but not significant relationship with student academic performance ($r = .177$; $N=110$; $p > .05$) while teacher introjected regulation and external regulation were found to have weak, negative but not significant relationship with student academic performance ($r = -.086$; $N=110$; $p > .05$) and ($r = -.146$; $N=110$; $p > .05$) respectively. The study concluded that teacher identified regulation, teacher introjected regulation, teacher external regulation and student academic performance did not have significant relationship with student academic performance. This means that the three variables were not a source of motivation for students academic performance, despite the fact that they are expected to motivate learners in academic performance. The findings of this study would inform the stakeholders in education in coming up with strategists to enhance teacher motivation so as to improve student academic performance.

KEY WORDS: Relationship between Teacher identified regulation, Teacher introjected regulation, Teacher external regulation, Student Academic performance, Kenya: Secondary Schools, Gem Sub County

INTRODUCTION

Motivation is a psychological process that influences individual behaviour with respect to the attainment of workplace goals and tasks (Bennell, 2004). A review of empirical studies on teacher motivation in Bangladesh, India and Pakistan indicates widespread low or decreasing level of teacher motivation resulting in lower quality of education (Bennell & Akyeampong, 2007). Similarly, a study conducted across Zambia, Papua New Guinea and Malawi found that teachers' motivation was both fragile and declining leading to low student academic performance. Teachers reported having low self-esteem in their roles and felt they were not respected by the community (Voluntary Service Overseas, 2002).

Jemila (2013) also did a study on the effects of motivation factors on teachers' performance in Tanzanian education institutions; A case study of public secondary schools in Nyamagana Sub- County Mwanza and found that there is an inadequate motivation of teachers and consequently low performance in public secondary schools. Likewise, Oyambu (2009) found that there was low teacher motivation in Masimba Division, Masaba South Sub-County in Kenya which also resulted to low student academic performance in public secondary schools.

In Siaya Sub-County, a report of 2015 by the county Education office revealed that teachers were devoting less time to co-curricular activities, teaching preparation and marking. In addition deteriorating standards of professional conducts including serious misbehaviour and poor professional performance had been observed in some secondary schools within Siaya Sub-County. These were indicators of lack of motivation among teachers thereby affecting performance in core functions like teaching effectively to produce results (Anusu, Barasa & Omulando, 2014). Likewise in Gem Sub-County, report of teachers' absenteeism, tardiness and general misconduct such as drunken behaviour were on the increase and these could be symptoms of low teacher motivation in the Sub-County (Gem Sub-County Education Office, 2012). Statistics also show that a large population of teachers in Secondary schools in Gem-Sub-County had enrolled in institutions of higher learning to pursue additional professional courses hoping to quite the teaching profession to other jobs perceived to be more satisfying (Mande, 2012). This implies that many teachers were resigning from teaching to other jobs indicating that there was low teacher motivation in the Sub-County resulting to low student academic performance.

Self-Determination theory links personality, human motivation and optimal functioning. It posits that there are two main types of motivation; intrinsic and extrinsic and that both are powerful forces in shaping who we are and how we behave (Deci & Ryan, 2008). Self-Determination theory focuses on the degree to which human behaviour is self motivated and self-determined. Work-Self-Determination Index may be useful when researchers want to select individuals who display either a Self-Determined or non Self-Determined motivational profile. According to Ryan and Connell (1989), teacher motivation can be measured using six motivational constructs including; intrinsic motivation, integrated regulation, identified regulation, introjected regulation, external regulation and amotivation where mean of each sub-scale is multiplied by the weights corresponding to the underlying levels of self-determination. The above studies found that there were low teacher motivation resulting to low student academic performance but did not incorporate the six constructs of teacher motivation in determining the motivation level of teachers.

Research Objective

The objective of the study was to establish the relationship between teacher identified regulation and student academic performance.

SYNTHESIS OF LITERATURE ON TEACHER IDENTIFIED REGULATION, TEACHER INTROJECTED REGULATION, TEACHER EXTERNAL REGULATION AND STUDENT ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

Extrinsic motivation can be defined as it pertains to a wide variety of behaviours that are engaged in a means to an end not for their own sake (Deci, 1975). People extrinsically motivated do an activity to obtain separate outcomes from the activity. For instance, "I am doing this task because I will receive a reward after I complete it". Self-Determination Theory researchers divide extrinsic motivation into four types, spread along the continuum from most to least externally controlled; these are external regulation, introjected regulation, identified regulation and integrated regulation. Furthermore, some studies grouped external and introjected regulations together, labelling it as non- autonomous (or controlled) extrinsic motivation and grouped identified and integrated regulations together as autonomous extrinsic motivation (Ryan & Deci, 2000). According to Vansteenkiste et al. 2010, identified regulation and intrinsic motivation are autonomous forms of motivation that involve the regulation of behaviour with the experience of volition, psychological freedom and reflective self-endorsement.

The first level is external regulation, where behaviour is guided by external control. At this level the reason why people behave is to obtain rewards or avoid punishment. Such regulations occur in the most controlling context and people's interests are not regarded. The second level, introjected regulation is still controlling but less than external regulation. People engage in activities because they either want to avoid the feeling of guilt or attain the feeling of approval. Because feeling guilt or approval is derived from the feeling of pressure, this introjected regulation is barely autonomous (Ryan & Deci 2000). The next level of extrinsic motivation is identified regulation. This regulation is less controlling and more autonomous than the previous level. According to this regulation people perform acts when they think they are valuable or important to achieve their goals (Rya & Deci, 2000). Thus, identified regulation is somewhat close to intrinsic motivation even though the personal importance is not from the intrinsic value (Eccles, 2005). The last level of extrinsic motivation is integrated regulation which is the most autonomous and the least controlling form. At this level, people engage in activities because the activity has been incorporated into their self of self. Integrated regulation is very similar to intrinsic motivation because the cause of behaviour is from the individual internal need. This regulation however still categorized

as extrinsic motivation because the outcomes of the behaviours (one's satisfaction and sense of self) are not intrinsically the behaviours per se (Ryan & Deci, 2000).

The literature has positively related integrated regulation and identified regulation to diverse desirable behaviour within the education setting such as persistence (Black & Deci, 2000), student academic performance (Borche, Srrazin, Grouzet, Pelletier & Chanal, 2008), cooperation and respect towards peers (Sanchez, et al. 2014) or the teacher performance (Aelterman et al., 2016). Similarly, according Reeve and Jang (2006), there is positive relationship between autonomous extrinsic motivations such as identified and integrated regulations and the student academic performance. Autonomous style of teaching promotes student inner motivational resources such as their interest and values by using practices such as allowing choice, spending time to communicate with students offering encouragement and providing rationales. With identified regulation people feel autonomously regulated and greater freedom because the behaviour is more congruent with their personal goals (Gagne & Deci, 2005). For example, if employees strongly value their work training and understand that addition training would be beneficial for their task performance, they would feel relatively autonomous during training even if the training is not intrinsically interesting.

In the contrary teachers are ability avoidance oriented which is very similar to introjected regulation, their students tend to regard their teacher as using controlled teaching practices such as pressure which negatively relates to student academic performance (Butler & Shibaz, 2008). Besides external regulation which refers to performing a task to obtain rewards or avoid punishment lies at the low end of the continuum; it is the least autonomous form of extrinsic motivation (Gagne et al. 2010). Both introjected regulation and external regulation are controlled forms of motivation involving the regulation of behaviour with the experience of pressure and are less self-determined. Introjected regulation, external regulation and amotivation have been positively related to undesirable behaviour outcomes; for example, school dropouts (Vallerand & Blasonnet, 1992), lack of attention in class (Stephens & Pantoja, 2016) or resentment towards equals and towards the teaching staff (Aelterman et al. 2016). In the context Kim and Cho (2014) observed that while pre-service teachers' intrinsic motivation positively predicts teachers sense of efficacy, during teaching practice, introjected regulation predicted their expectation of reality shock.

Jing Zhang et al. (2016) Conducted a study on the different relations of extrinsic introjected identified regulation and intrinsic motivation on employee performance and found that identified regulation significantly predicted interpersonal performance and adaptive performance. External regulation, introjected regulation and intrinsic motivation had no significant impact on interpersonal adaptive task or dedicative performance. The study concluded that only identified regulation strongly predict work performance.

Extrinsic motivation, in contrast to intrinsic motivation, requires an instrumentality between the activity and some separable consequences such as tangible or verbal rewards, so satisfaction comes not from the activity itself but rather from the extrinsic consequences to which the activity leads (Deci et al. 1991; Ryan & Connell, 1989). That is, the behaviour is not performed for its own sake, but instead to receive a reward or to avoid some punishment once the behaviour has ended (Pelletier et al. 1997). According to Fryer (2011), one potential method to increase student achievement and improve the quality of individuals selecting the teaching as a profession is to provide teacher with financial incentives based on student achievement. Double Gist (2013), also asserts that irregular payment of teacher's salaries adversely affects teaching and learning in schools. Hence teachers refuse to teach and consequently, some subjects are not taught in the schools and that hinders the effective teaching learning resulting to poor academic performance. Nonetheless, Cherrington, Reily and Scott (1971) reported that there is inherent relationship between work performance and satisfaction that is relative to reward. Kopelman also reported that the stronger the relationship between job performance and rewards, the higher the expectancy that the effort expended will lead to reward.

However, Deci and Ryan (1996; 1992) provide evidence that extrinsically caused behaviour undermines motivation in the long run. Consequently, Benabou and Triole (2000) also reports that incentives are only rein forcers of motivation in the short run and negative rein forcers in the long run. In particular, Holmn, Strom and Milgrom, (1991); Jacob and Levitt (2003), point out that, if teacher incentives have unintended consequences such as explicit cheating, teaching to the test or focusing on the specific tested objectives at the expense of more general learning, teacher incentive could have a negative impact on students' performance. Similarly some argue that teacher incentives can decrease a teacher intrinsic motivation or lead to harmful competition between teachers in what some believes to be collaborative environment (Johnson, 1994; Firestone & Pennell, 1983).

Mugikuu (2012), conducted a study on influence of teachers’ motivation on students’ performance in Kenya Certificate of Secondary education in public secondary schools in Kwale County. The findings revealed that teachers’ working conditions (extrinsic) affected performance of students in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education. Gitonga (2012) also carried out a study on influence of teachers’ motivation on students’ performance in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education in public secondary schools in Imenti South Sub-County Kenya and found that working conditions provided conducive learning atmosphere for teachers to perform better hence good student performance in examinations. The study also concluded that there was a strong relationship between remuneration related factors (extrinsic) and student academic performance in Secondary schools.

According to Koech (2014), on influence of extrinsic rewards on teachers’ job commitment in public primary schools, Sigor Division, Chepalugu Sub-county Kenya, most teachers (52.5%) failed to get recommendation in school and this may have reduced contact hours with the learners. The majority of the teachers (61.7%) noted that the household items offered to them were less diverse. The study established that majority (71.7%) of public primary schools did not provide meals for teachers as a result most teachers were demotivated to teach which resulted to poor student academic performance. Similarly, Opiyo (2010) on his study about job satisfaction and motivational needs of teachers of Migori Sub-County contends that teachers of Religious Education were working under poor conditions because teaching materials and other equipment were not adequately supplied in most secondary schools in Migori Sub-County leading to teacher dissatisfaction and poor student performance. These studies reveal that there is a positive relationship between extrinsic teacher motivation and student academic performance but did not analyse the relationship between each component of extrinsic teacher motivation and student academic performance.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study was guided by conceptual framework based on self-determination theory by Rayn and Connel (1989). Figure 1 is a Conceptual Framework which is an illustration of the various variables that play a role in teacher motivation in secondary schools. Self-Determination Theory is a macro theory of human motivation and personality that concerns people growth tendencies and innate psychological needs. It focuses on the degree to which human behaviour is self-motivated and self-Determined. According to this theory, intrinsic motivation and each type of extrinsic motivation are reflected in different reasons for behaving and these reasons provide a means for assessing the type of motivation. Teacher motivation can be measured using six motivational constructs including; intrinsic motivation, integrated regulation, identified regulation, introjected regulation, external regulation and amotivation where mean of each sub-scale is multiplied by the weights corresponding to the underlying levels of self-determination (Ryan & Connell, 1989).

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework showing the relationship between teacher identified regulation, teacher introjected regulation, teacher external regulation and student academic performance

The framework in Figure 1 shows the relationship between the independent and the dependent variables of the study. The dependent variable was student performance measured by students mean scores in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education examination while the independent variables were the teacher identified regulation, teacher introjected regulation and teacher external regulation. The influence of independent variables were moderated by intervening variables. For instance, students entry behaviour and teaching and learning resources. These are called the intervening variables. The researcher however held these intervening variables constant to enable the determination of relationship between independent and dependent variables.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a correlation and descriptive research designs and was guided by the Conceptual Framework based on Self-Determination Theory. The study population was 41 principals and 180 teachers from 41 schools. A pilot study was carried out in five schools with five principals and 19 teachers. The remaining 36 public secondary schools and 36 principals were picked through saturated sampling technique while purposive sampling technique was used to select 110 teachers who had taught the same class from form three to form four between 2013-2014. Data was collected using questionnaires, interview schedule and document analysis guide. Work Self-Determination Index was used to measure teacher motivation. Reliability of the instruments was established by test-retest method and a coefficient index of .791 was accepted. Content validity of the instruments was ascertained by three experts in the area within the department. Pearson Correlation coefficient and regression analysis were used to analyse the quantitative data while qualitative data from interview schedule was analysed on an ongoing process as themes and sub-themes emerged.

RESULTS

Demographic characteristics of Respondents

This section presents the demographic information. The demographic data of teachers were based on their gender, type of school, age, professional qualification and teaching experience. Demographic information helps to find the authenticity of the data by giving a reliable data. The data on these variables are as shown in Table 1 and Table 2 for principals and teachers respectively.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Teachers as indicated by teachers

(n= 110)

Demographic Characteristics	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	76	69.0
Female	34	31.0
Total	110	100
Type of School		
County boys boarding	13	11.9
County girls boarding	21	19.0
Sub –County mixed boarding	42	38.1
Sub-County mixed day	34	31.0
Total	110	100
Age in years		
20-29	4	3.6
30-39	72	65.4
40-49	31	28.6
50 and above	3	2.4
Total	110	100
Highest Professional Qualification		
Diploma	5	4.8
Bachelor of education	99	90.5

Master in education	3	2.4
PhD	3	2.4
Total	110	100
Number of years served in current station		
06 – 11		
12 - 17	59	53.6
18 and above	34	30.9
Total	17	15.5
	110	100

According to Table 1, the total male respondents were 76(69%) while female respondents were 34(31%). Teachers who filled questionnaire from county boys boarding schools were 13(11.9%), those from county girls' boarding schools were 21 (19%) sub county mixed boarding schools were 42(38.1%) whereas those from Sub County mixed day schools were 34 (31%). This implies that teachers who participated in this study were mainly from Sub-County mixed boarding schools and Sub-County mixed day schools of Gem Sub-county. Regarding the age, those within the ages of 20-29 years were 4 (3.6%), those within 30-39 years were 72 (65.4%), those within 40-49 years were 31 (28.6%) while those within 50 and above were only 3 (2.4%). Hence, it can be concluded that the teacher representation in the schools so interviewed were youthful within the age brackets of 20-39 years. On the levels of education, teachers with diploma were 5 (4.8%), those with bachelor's degree were 99 (90.5%) while those with either a master or a PhD degree were 3 (2.4%) each. This indicates that teachers in the Sub-County were professionally trained. The information shows that all categories of teachers were involved.

Academic Performance in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education 2014, Gem Sub-County

Academic performance was measured in terms of the mean grade each teacher achieved per subject taught. Table 2 shows the summary of teacher subject mean score in the Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education for 2014.

Table 2: Teacher Subject Mean Score in the Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education 2014, (n = 110)

Subject Mean Score	Number of Teachers	Percentage (%)
1 – 2	0	0
3 – 4	31	28.18
5 – 6	60	54.55
7 – 8	17	15.46
9 – 10	2	1.82
Total	110	100

According to Table 2 there was no respondent with a subject mean score between (1- 2) out of possible score of 12. There were 31(28.18%) teachers with a subject mean score between (3 - 4), 60 (54.55%) teachers with a mean score between (5 - 6) in their subjects, 17 (15.46%) teachers with a mean score between (7 - 8) and 2 (1.82%) teachers with a mean score between (9 - 10) in their subjects. It can be concluded that teachers in Gem Sub-County averagely scored a mean between (5 - 6) in their subjects.

Objective One

The research objective was to determine the relationship between teacher identified regulation and student academic performance

Table 3: Ratings of Teacher Identified Regulation, n = 110

Identified regulation Index	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
0.00 – 4.80	99	90.00
4.81 – 9.60	11	10.00
9.61 – 14.40	00	0.00

14.41 – 19.20	00	0.00
19.21 – 24.00	00	0.00
Total	110	100

Interpretation of Identified Regulation Indices:

- 00 – 4.80=Very Low Identified Regulation;**
- 4.81 – 9.60=Low Identified Regulation;**
- 9.61 – 14.40=Moderately Low Identified Regulation;**
- 14.41- 19.20=High Identified Regulation;**
- 19.21- 24.00=Very High Identified Regulation.**

Concerning teacher identified regulation, Table 3 indicate that, 99 (90%) teachers had Very Low identified regulation, 11(10%) teachers had Low identified regulation, whereas no teacher had Moderately Low or High or Very High identified regulation.

In order to establish the relationship between teacher identified regulation and student academic performance, data on identified regulation and student academic performance were correlated and regression analysis computed (Table 4 & 5)

Table 4 shows a correlation matrix between teacher identified regulation and student academic performance.

Table 4: Correlation Matrix between Teacher Identified Regulation and Student Academic Performance

		Student Academic Performance
Identified regulation	Pearson Correlation	.177
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.065
	<i>N</i>	110

Regarding Table 4, the numerical value of the correlation coefficient is .177, which indicates the presence of a weak and positive relationship between identified teacher regulation and student academic performance.

In order to confirm whether teacher identified regulation is a significant predictor of student academic performance or not, (Table 5) was generated.]

Table 5: Analysis of Variance between Teacher Identified Regulation and Student Academic Performance

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5.648	1	5.648	3.476	.065
	Residual	175'490	108	1.625		
	Total	181.138	109			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), identified regulation

According to Table 5, teacher identified regulation is not a predictor of student academic performance ($F(1, 108) = 3.476; p = .065$). Linear regression analysis therefore could not be generated. The results of this study reveal that there was weak, positive but not significant relationship between teacher identified regulation and student academic performance.

Objective Two

The research objective was to determine the relationship between teacher introjected regulation and student academic performance. Introjected teacher regulation was then determined by multiplying the mean of introjected regulation factors by the weight (-1). In order to determine the level of teacher introjected regulation, (Table 6) was computed.

Table 6: Ratings of Teacher Introjected Regulation, (n=110)

Introjected regulation Index	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
0.00 – 4.80	101	91.82
4.81 – 9.60	9	8.18
9.61 – 14.40	00	0.00
14.41 – 19.20	00	0.00
19.21 – 24.00	00	0.00
Total	110	100

Interpretation of Introjected Regulation Indices:
00 – 4.80=Very Low introjected regulation;
4.81 – 9.60=Low introjected regulation;
9.61 – 14.40=Moderately Low introjected regulation;
14.41- 19.20=High introjected regulation;
19.21- 24.00=Very High introjected regulation.

On teacher introjected regulation, Table 6 indicate that, 101 (91.82%) teachers had Very Low iintrojected regulation, 9(8.18%) teachers had Low introjected regulation, while no teacher had Moderately Low or High or Very High introjected regulation

To establish the relationship between teacher introjected regulation and student academic performance, data on introjected regulation and student academic performance were correlated and regression analysis computed (Table 7 and 8).

Table 7 shows a correlation matrix between teacher introjected regulation and student academic performance.

Table 7: Correlation Matrix between Introjected Regulation and Student Academic Performance

		Student Academic Performance
Introjected regulation	Pearson Correlation	-.086
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.372
	N	110

Regarding Table 7, the numerical value of the correlation coefficient is -.086, which indicates the presence of a weak and negative relationship between introjected teacher regulation and student academic performance. This means that as introjected regulation increases, student academic performance decreases. When one teaches just to succeed in the job or not to be ashamed, students are likely to register low performance. The probability value is .372 indicating no significant relationship meaning that teacher introjected regulation cannot explain student academic performance. This conforms to Jian Zhang et al. (2016) who found that there was no significant relationship between introjected regulation and work performance that could yield good results.

To confirm whether teacher introjected regulation is a significant predictor of student academic performance or not, (Table 8) was generated.

Table 8: Analysis of Variance between Teacher Introjected Regulation and Student Academic Performance

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	1.340	1	1.340	.805	.372
1 Residual	179.798	108	1.665		
Total	181.138	109			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance
 b. Predictors: (Constant), introjected regulation

Regarding Table 8, teacher introjected regulation is not a predictor of student academic performance ($F(1, 108) = 0.805; p = .372$) hence regression analysis could not be generated.

Objective Three

The research objective was to determine the relationship between teacher external regulation and student academic performance. The teacher motivation questionnaire was used to obtain information regarding external teacher regulation. The questionnaire was developed using external regulation factors as motivators. External teacher regulation was then determined by multiplying the mean of external regulation factors by the weight (-2).

In order to determine the teacher external motivation level (Table 9 was computed).

Table 9: Ratings of Teacher External Regulation, $n = 110$

External regulation Index	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
0.00 – 4.80	6	5.45
4.81 – 9.60	94	85.46
9.61 – 14.40	10	9.09
14.41 – 19.20	00	0.00
19.21 – 24.00	00	0.00
Total	110	100

Interpretation of External Regulation Indices:

00 – 4.80=Very Low External Regulation;

4.81– 9.60=Low External Regulation;

9.61–14.40=Moderately Low External Regulation;

14.41-19.20=High External Regulation;

19.21- 24.00=Very High External Regulation.

Regarding Table 9, six (5.45%) teachers had Very Low external regulation, 94(85.46%) teachers had Low external regulation, 10 (9.09%) teachers had Moderately Low external regulation and no teacher had High or Very High external regulation.

To establish the relationship between teacher external regulation and student academic performance, data on external regulation and student academic performance were correlated and regression analysis computed (Table 10 and 11).

Table 10 shows a correlation matrix between teacher external regulation and student academic performance.

Table 10: Correlation Matrix between Teacher External Regulation and Student Academic Performance

		Student Academic performance
External regulation	Pearson Correlation	-.146
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.128
	<i>N</i>	110

According to Table 10, the correlation coefficient is -.146, which indicates the presence of a weak and negative relationship between external regulation and student academic performance. It therefore means that as external regulation increases, student academic performance decreases. When teachers teaches to earn money or to get income, they are not more concerned with the academic performance of student; they give assignments but fails to mark; they don't go extra mile with the student if there is no supervision or material reward resulting to decrease in the student academic performance. The probability value is .128 indicating that relationship between external regulation and student academic performance is not significant. It therefore means that external regulation cannot be relied on to explain student academic performance.

In order to confirm whether teacher external regulation is a significant predictor of student academic performance or no, (Table 11) was generated.

Table 11: Analysis of Variance between Teacher External Regulation and Student Academic Performance

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3.868	1	3.868	2.358	1.28
	Residual	177.269	108	1.641		
	Total	181.138	109			
a.	Dependent Variable: Performance					
b.	Predictors: (Constant), external regulation					

According to Table 11, external regulation is not a predictor of student academic performance ($F(1, 108) = 2.358; p = 1.28$), and therefore linear regression analysis cannot be generated. It can be concluded from the study findings that there is weak, negative and not significant relationship between teacher external regulation and student academic performance. The findings of this

DISCUSSION

The relationship between teacher integrated regulation and student academic performance.

Teachers in Gem Sub-County had low integrated regulation, meaning that teachers were not engaging in teaching activity because the activity had been incorporated in their self. Furthermore, integrated regulation is the most autonomous and least controlling form of extrinsic motivation which is also very similar to intrinsic motivation (Ryan & Deci, 2000). This study therefore implies that there was limited use of autonomy style of instructing students by teachers of Gem Sub-County, meaning that student’s inner motivational resources such as their interest and values could not be well promoted. Reeve and Jang (2006) stated that student inner motivational resources such as their interest and values are promoted by using practices such as allowing choice for students, spending time to communicate with students, offering encouragements to students and providing rationales to students which are autonomy style of instructing students. Similarly Bolt et al., (1999) found that if teachers are autonomously motivated, they are more likely to behave autonomy- supportive ways such as promoting students’ inner motivational resources by providing student centred lessons, valuing task and using non-controlling conversations. Since the integration regulation (autonomous) level of teachers in Gem Sub-County was low, their autonomy – supportive ways for students was also low implying that they were not using instructional practices that satisfy the need for autonomy for the students and therefore, their input was limited hence student gained very little from their teaching activities. Interview findings were also in agreement with these findings where the principals remarked that teacher integrated regulation was low. The following responses were expressed by a principal from the interview schedule. There is low teacher integrated regulation level; Teachers are not performing their duties because teaching has become fundamental part of who they are or because teaching is part of their life but for the external rewards such as monetary rewards they get from teaching. They are not always willing to go extra mile with the students engaging them to more academic work during remedial lessons if there is no payment for the extra work done. Besides, teachers do not frequently administer assignments and continuous assessment test to students unless they are pressurised by the principals to do so. There is a moderate relationship between teacher integrated regulation and student academic performance.

All these factors have a bearing on teacher motivation because teaching is dynamic and teachers are also looking forward for promotion. For instance, male teachers are motivated than female teachers because female teachers’ demands are more of domestic work while male teachers demands are more of promotion. Likewise, young teachers need motivation than old teachers because they still aim higher and need promotion. Teachers in County schools are motivated because of high students’ entry behaviour and more teaching and learning resources in their schools than teachers in Sub-County schools. Similarly, high qualified teachers are motivated to teach because they have the content than the low qualified teachers and able to teach effectively to produce good results.

Teacher identified regulation was very low meaning that teachers in Gem Sub-County were not performing their duties to identify themselves with the value of teaching. This is according to Ryan and Deci (2000), who stated that according this regulation, people perform acts when they think they are valuable or important to achieve their goals. It therefore implies that there was poor syllabus

coverage, poor lesson attendance, low mastery of content by teachers and unwillingness to go extra mile with the students. Additionally, teacher identified regulation is an autonomous motivation where teachers uses practices which satisfy the autonomy support of students. It therefore means that there was limited use of practices such as spending time to communicate with the students, allowing choice for students, offering encouragement and providing rationales to students. They were not identifying themselves with the teaching activities implying that their level of commitment to work was low. This conforms to Jing Zhang et al. (2016) who found that identified regulation significantly predicted interpersonal performance, adaptive performance or dedicative performance. This means that teacher's input was limited hence students gained very little from their teaching activities. Interview findings conforms to these findings where a principal argued that teacher identified regulation was low. In this respect the principal expressed that: "Teacher identified regulation is low; teachers are not always clearing the syllabus in time meaning that syllabus coverage is always poor, they are not attending all their lessons as per the master time table meaning that their level of commitment to teach is very low. Teachers are not willing to engage students in more continuous assessment test and assignments during extra lesson hours and do the marking if there is no monetary reward for it neither do they avail themselves for the students to consult them after normal lesson hours unless there is pay. Teachers do not show any evidence that they are teaching to attain certain important objectives, lifestyles or career goals. There is a moderate relationship between teacher identified regulation and student academic performance.

Identified regulation increases student academic performance also increases. This is in line with the findings by Borche et al. (2008) who concluded that teacher identified regulation categorised as autonomous motivation is positively related to student academic performance. It therefore means that when the behaviour of a teacher is conducted because the behaviour social value is appreciated or when teachers are performing their duties when they think that they are valuable or important to achieve their goals, student academic performance also increases. However, the probability value is .065 meaning that the relationship is not significant and teacher identified regulation cannot be relied on to explain student academic performance. These contradict the findings by Jian zhang et al. (2016) who found out that identified regulation of employees significantly predicted work performance. Implying that teacher identified regulation significantly predict their work performance which is significantly related to student academic performance. The findings of the study also is not in agreement with Reeve, (2002) and Jang, (2006) who found out that autonomous teacher motivation is related to teaching practices that enhances student academic performance. This means that teacher identified regulation which is an autonomous motivation encourages the use of teaching practices such as offering encouragement to students, spending time to communicate with students and providing rationale to students which are significantly related to student academic performance.

With identified regulation, people feel autonomously regulated and greater freedom because the behaviour is more congruent with their personal goals (Gagne & Deci, 2005). The study finding confirms the findings by Black and Deci (2000) who concluded that teacher identified regulation is positively related to teacher's persistence to work which enhances student academic performance. This is also supported by Pelletier et al. (2008) who found out that there is positive relationship between teacher identified regulation and student academic performance. Regardless of insignificant relationship between teacher identified regulation and student academic performance, there is still need for teachers to improve in their identified regulation because it is an autonomous extrinsic motivation which promote student inner motivational resources thereby enhancing student academic performance.

Borche (2008) stated that teacher integrated regulation is positively related to student academic performance. When teachers engage in teaching because it is part of their life or because teaching is part of the way in which they have chosen to lead their lives they take more time with the students explaining the content of the syllabus in details enabling the students to understand hence improving in their academic performance. The relationship is also significant ($p = .000$) meaning that teacher integrated regulation can be relied on to explain student academic performance. This conforms to the findings by Koesner et al. (2008) who stated that autonomous teacher motivations are closely related to greater student success. This means that teacher integrated regulation which is categorized as autonomous motivation is likely to be significantly related to student academic performance.

Relationship between Teacher Introjected Regulation and Student Academic Performance

Teachers in Gem Sub-County have Very low introjected regulation meaning that teachers were not engaging in teaching because they either want to avoid the feeling of guilt or to attain the feeling of approval as stated by Ryan and Deci,(2000) who concluded that feeling of guilt or approval is derived from the feeling of pressure and is barely autonomous. This means that teachers in Gem

Sub-County do not feel pressure from above such as accountability or responsibility of student achievement hence they do not tend to adopt controlling teaching styles rather than autonomy- supportive teaching style (Reeve, 2009). Additionally, teachers in Gem Sub-County are not ability avoidance oriented as indicated by Butler and Shibaz, (2008) who stated that if teachers are ability avoidance oriented which is very similar to introjected regulation, the students tend to regard their teacher as using controlled teaching practices such pressure. According to this finding, teachers' level of commitment to work should be high meaning that their input should high and students should gain a lot from their teaching activities. Interview findings disagreed with these findings where a principal argued that teacher introjected regulation was high. In this respect the principal stated that:

Teacher introjected regulation was high; quite a number of teachers engaged in teaching due to guilt, compulsion or to maintain their self-worth. They don't teach because teaching is interesting or enjoyable and therefore are not willing to go extra mile with the students or engage them in more academic work which could yield good academic performance. They do not do a lot of research or prepare adequately for the lesson hence not able to deliver the lesson content well for the students enhancing low student academic performance. There is low relationship between teacher introjected regulation and student academic performance.

It can be concluded from this study findings that there is weak, negative and non-significant relationship between teacher introjected regulation and student academic performance. According to this motivational construct, people engage in activities because they either want to avoid the feeling guilt or attain the feeling of approval. The feeling of guilt or approval is derived from the feeling of pressure which is barely autonomous or controlled (Ryan & Deci, 2000) which have negative impact on student academic performance. There should be minimal introjected regulation among teachers in order to produce good results in the student academic performance

It can be therefore concluded that there was low teacher external regulation in Gem-Sub-County meaning that teachers in Gem Sub-County were not performing their duties to achieve rewards or to avoid punishment as stated by Gagne et al. (2010). This means that teachers in Gem Sub-County were willing to go extra mile with students even if there was no external reward for the work done. It also means that there were limited undesirable behaviour outcomes such as school dropouts (Vallerand & Blasonnette, 1992), lack of attention in class (Stephenes & Pantaja, 2016) or resentment towards equals and towards the teaching staff (Aelternam et al. 2016) which are related to external regulation. This implies that teachers in Gem Sub-County were committed to their work and regarded the interest of their students. However, interview findings were not in agreement to these findings where a principal remarked that teacher external regulation was high. In this respect a principal stated that teacher external regulation is high; quite a number of teachers perform their duties to earn salary, to obtain reward or to avoid punishment. They are not always willing to go extra mile with students or make themselves available for students for consultations if there are no external rewards. Teachers are not willing to engage their students in more assignments, continuous assessment tests and joint exams if there is no monetary reward for marking the scripts unless they are pressurized by the principal. There is low relationship between teacher external regulation and student academic performance.

Th findings of this study concur with Gagne et al. (2010) who concluded that external regulation which refers to performing a task to obtain rewards is the least autonomous form of extrinsic motivation. Just like introjected regulation, external regulation is a controlled form of motivation involving the regulation of behaviour with an experience of presser and are less self-determined thereby impacting negatively on the student academic performance. Further to that, external regulation has been positively related to undesirable behaviour outcomes such as school dropouts (Vallerand & Blasonnet, 1992) and lack of attention in class (Stephenes & Pantoja, 2016). This is supported by Jing Zhang et al. (2016) who found out that external regulation had no significant impact on dedicative performance which produces good results. Teachers external regulation should be minimized or avoided because it hinders effective teaching and learning resulting to poor student academic performance.

CONCLUSION

Concerning the findings of the study on the relationship between teacher identified regulation and student academic performance, the study concluded that identified regulation had a weak and positive but not significant relationship with student academic performance.

The relationship between teacher introjected regulation, teacher external regulation and student academic performance was weak and negative but not significant.

RECOMMENDATION

The three variables namely teacher identified regulation, teacher introjected regulation and teacher external regulations should be managed strategically in the best practice possible so as to enhance students academic performance. This implies that the practising teachers should be adequately trained so that they are competent in delivering these regulations as desired in the interest of student motivation that should culminate in improved student performance.

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